

EMEBEDDING GENDER APPROACH IN INTERNATIONAL RESEARCH: AN EXAMPLE OF A EUROPEAN PROJECT ON FORCED MIGRATION

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Gender aspects remain challenging in today's research and innovation environment, let alone reaching equity in the global society. According to World Economic Forums report for 2020, today's active generation will not see gender equity in our lifetimes as it will be not reached for 99,5 years. Gender gaps in current international research can be better understood if we consider gender equality from a broader perspective, including economic participation and opportunity, health and survival, political empowerment and educational attainment in each of the countries that participate in a project (WEF, 2020) and consider the cultural and religious norms that guide the understanding of the term gender around the world. These are the underlying elements upon which gender equity is constructed and determine the level of difficult of embedding gender to an international project, with diverse starting point in each country.

In real world social research settings with participatory focus, gender equality practice can represent huge challenges in terms of discrimination, contrary attitudes and long lived social norms, especially when it comes to research habits. If observed under an intersectional point of view and considering that the project focused on vulnerable collectives among the forcibly displaced people, the challenges double. Special requirements apply when researching highly vulnerable people and people in forced displacement. The current paper delves into the reality of a European H2020 project with the aim of exploring how diverse aspects of gender were transversally embedded into the research process in seven participating countries, including partner from Europe and Middle East. Though gender balance in research teams, work division and decision making have become a must in Horizon projects, and gender focus in all research stages recommendable, putting these aspects into practice proved to be highly challenging. The specific objective of the paper is to show how gender equity aspects were integrated into the project team, research practice and resulting innovation activities. Exploring if it would be possible to move from merely gender-aware and -sensitive practices to entirely gender-responsive and even gender-transformative approaches was also included in the study.

From the methodology perspective, the paper uses case study and participatory observation methods. It shows a practical case of embedding gender into a project -the research concept, structures and practice- in a highly culturally diverse and demanding research setting, with very specific initial gender requirements, included in the project's Grant Agreement. It offers an inside vision of the project, the difficulties and benefits of reaching towards fully gender responsive responses in international settings and in the daily research practice.

The results show that initial training in gender and the related concept of Responsible Research and Innovation are required, and constant reminders about relative aspects are recommended. The integration of gender in the structures of the research environment and intersectional application during all the phases of the project are described, including partners' insights about how this task was accomplished. The level of integration was considered mostly gender-responsive, with a few advances towards the level of gender-transformative action. Finally, as a learning result from the project experience, a step to step guide to embedding gender in R&I is offered.

Keywords: Gender, Intersectional approach, Gender-responsive, Forced Migrants, EU research.